

Structure of dynamics theories quantum gravity

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Quantum gravity is unification the quantum theory and the general relativity. Problem: the physics of time asymmetry and how nature works.

A first course in quantum gravity [1]. A radical new vision for time in quantum gravity

$$\left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial t}\right)^3 + \frac{\partial S}{\partial t}\left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial t}\right)^2 + \frac{\partial^3 S}{\partial t^3} = G\hbar \cdot \Gamma$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{2} e^{\alpha\beta\gamma} F_\alpha^i \left(\frac{\partial F_{i\beta}}{\partial x_\gamma} + \frac{\partial F_{\gamma\beta}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial F_{i\gamma}}{\partial x_\beta} \right)$$

$$F_\gamma^\alpha = \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial x_\alpha \partial x_\gamma} + \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_\alpha} \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_\gamma}$$

The local phase the quantum evolution

$$S = S(x, y, z, t)$$

$$\psi = A \cdot e^{i \cdot S}$$

Higher speculations: the ultimate arrow of time is non-linear gauge foam the space-time.

The road to reality: the search for the Meta-Laws and new directions for the physics of time.

[1] Classical gravity and gauge flow, V. Kuyukov, 2021, osf.preprints.